

The Leibniz Data Manager: Supporting Researchers in the Lifecycle of Research Data

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1 Introduction and Motivation

Research Data Management (RDM) involves the systematic organization, storage, preservation, and sharing of data throughout a research project's lifecycle. Its primary goal is to ensure effective handling, maintenance, and accessibility of data, supporting the reproducibility, transparency, and integrity of research outcomes, crucial aspects for the reliability and trustworthiness of scientific research [1]. The surge in digital research data in the late 20th century necessitated standardized practices. Recognizing data's pivotal role in advancing science, funding agencies formalized policies for data sharing and management. Exemplary initiatives, such as those led by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) in the USA¹ and the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) in Germany², underline the commitment to transparency and collaboration. These initiatives highlight the pivotal role of research data management in scientific reproducibility, transparency, and excellence, fostering collaboration across disciplines to establish legally compliant, interoperable, and sustainable data infrastructures [1], [2].

The FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and reproducible guidelines guide the publication and exchange of research digital objects and their metadata. While research data repositories are valuable, they fall short in holistically managing scientific objects and data, hindering computational transparency over

¹<https://data.library.arizona.edu/data-management/nih-data-management-sharing-policy-2023>

²<https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>

Figure 1. Overview of the Leibniz Data Manager

time. The resulting heterogeneity in data and metadata standards, APIs, file formats, licensing, archival guidelines, and more, makes searching across repositories time-consuming for researchers seeking data, necessitating a strategic approach. Geisler et al. [3] outline requirements for an effective data ecosystem, positioning knowledge-driven data ecosystems as frameworks for enhancing transparency in data exchange. Despite these efforts and relevant initiatives, a study published at Nature Index in 2019³ reveals that scientists are not totally familiar with FAIR principles, and data management plans are complicated to apply. Similarly, a survey conducted within the German neuroscience community shed light on prevailing challenges in research data management [4]. Barriers include a lack of standardized data and metadata, limited provenance tracking, insufficient infrastructure for sensitive data, low literacy, and constrained resources. The results underscore the need for systematic development of standards, tools, and infrastructure, coupled with training and support initiatives, emphasizing the role of effective data management in facilitating data sharing in research communities.

2 The Leibniz Data Manager

The *Leibniz Data Manager* (LDM) [5] aims to address these challenges and support researchers in the lifecycle of research data management. With features designed to streamline data organization, enhance metadata management, and ensure compliance with FAIR principles, the Leibniz Data Manager serves as a resource for researchers seeking to overcome barriers in effective research data management, see Figure 1. LDM publishes various types of research digital objects (RDO) following the FAIR principles, including datasets in different formats (e.g., CSV, JSON, or XML), data services

³<https://www.nature.com/nature-index/news/what-scientists-need-to-know-about-fair-data>

demonstrated as live code using Jupyter notebooks, and data visualizations (e.g., 2D and 3D support). The LDM dashboard allows researchers not only to manage research digital objects (e.g., collecting and searching) but also to analyze them using analytical methods implemented as Jupyter notebooks or using integrated visualization tools. Additionally, to ensure a persistent and global identification of RODs, LDM provides the option to generate a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)⁴ for each uploaded ROD, making them citeable, and giving the original authors credit for publishing their data if others reuse it. LDM is implemented as an open source and extends the open data repository system CKAN⁵ along with extra features developed on top of CKAN.

In addition to publishing RODs, LDM offers researchers the possibility of importing RODs already published in other repositories, such as the Leibniz University Hannover⁶, PANGAEA⁷, or RADAR⁸. Additionally, datasets and software published in GitHub repositories can be imported into LDM. These RODs are logically integrated into LDM, i.e., RODs are kept in the original repository, but their metadata descriptions are generated by LDM. A scheduler for synchronization allows LDM to maintain up-to-date descriptions. Metadata is expressed using existing vocabularies, e.g., DCAT⁹, DataCite¹⁰, and DublinCore¹¹. SKOS¹² and the Provenance Ontology (Prov-O)¹³ describe RODs' features (e.g., definitions and labels) and their provenance, respectively.

LDM creates a knowledge graph (KG) with the metadata of the RODs published by LDM users or imported from other repositories. RODs in the LDM KG are described in terms of the properties of a DCAT resource (e.g., creator, format, size, and distribution); also, the licenses that regulate the distribution and use of RODs are described in the KG. In case an ROD is related to a scientific publication, the description of the ROD in the LDM KG is linked to the description of this publication, e.g., its fine-grained representation in the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG)¹⁴. RODs are also linked to resources in Wikidata that provide a more detailed description of an ROD. The LDM KG is accessible via a SPARQL endpoint¹⁵, and DeTrusty [6], a federated query engine, allows for the execution of queries over the LDM, ORKG, and Wikidata KGs¹⁶.

LDM is publicly available¹⁷ at the TIB - Leibniz Information Center for Science and Technology in Hannover¹⁸. Additionally, LDM is also published as a Docker container to facilitate installing LDM distributions¹⁹. The main features of LDM are demonstrated in an open accessible demo²⁰.

⁴<https://www.doi.org/>

⁵<https://ckan.org/>

⁶<https://data.uni-hannover.de/>

⁷<https://www.pangaea.de/>

⁸<https://www.radar-service.eu/radar/en/home>

⁹<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

¹⁰<https://schema.datacite.org/>

¹¹<https://www.dublincore.org/>

¹²<https://www.w3.org/TR/2008/WD-skos-reference-20080829/skos.html>

¹³<https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

¹⁴<https://orkg.org/>

¹⁵https://labs.tib.eu/sdm/ldm_kg/sparql

¹⁶https://labs.tib.eu/sdm/ldm_federated/sparql

¹⁷<https://service.tib.eu/ldmservice/>

¹⁸<https://www.tib.eu/en/research-development/scientific-data-management/>

¹⁹https://github.com/SDM-TIB/LDM_Docker/

²⁰<https://service.tib.eu/ldmservice/demo>

3 Conclusions and Future Directions

LDM emerges as a timely framework, contributing to ongoing initiatives focused on improving transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration in the dynamic field of Research Data Management. By integrating FAIR principles and Semantic Web technologies, such as vocabularies, KGs, SPARQL endpoints, and query engines, LDM stands out as a key player in addressing current challenges and fostering a more efficient research data ecosystem. These specific features of LDM underscore the critical role that FAIR principles and Semantic Web technologies play in addressing the complexities of research data management. Looking ahead, our research plan includes the definition of hybrid AI systems that enhance the connections between LDM, ORKG, and Wikidata KGs. This will provide fine-grained and detailed metadata of scholarly resources to better support the research data lifecycle.

Author contributions

Philipp D. Rohde: Software, Validation, Investigation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision

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Mazen Bechara: Software, Validation, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing

Susanne Arndt: Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing

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Competing interests

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